

IMPROVEMENT OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS OF INSURANCE INSTITUTIONS

Bakhriev Dilshod Rizvonkulovich

The Banking and finance academy Republic of Uzbekistan

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Modern insurance is an integral part of the economy, which employs millions of people in various professions. An insurance organization performs a special function in the formation, distribution and use of insurance funds of funds in order to protect citizens from the risks of possible loss of values of tangible or other assets and reimburse them for losses in the event of an unfavorable event.

In the current economic and crisis conditions, the activities of insurance companies are carried out in a competitive environment, and the financial condition of an insurance company is a key factor in ensuring its life in a market economy.

However, the solution of practical problems of solvency for the modern insurance market of Uzbekistan is limited by their insufficient theoretical justification and methodological support. In the insurance literature, the understanding of solvency is limited by the ability to fulfill only insurance obligations, which narrows the scope of research. The experience of foreign approaches, such as Solvency I and Solvency II, which have successfully functioned and are functioning in Western countries, is mainly considered, but these models may not suit the modern specifics of the domestic market, as well as the specifics of doing business in Uzbekistan. The plan to comply with international standards should be achieved not by drastic, momentary reforms that will negatively affect the insurance companies themselves, but through sound policies aimed at the long term.

The problem of ensuring the solvency of insurance organizations is given special attention by state regulatory bodies of different countries. In international insurance practice, even in conditions of a stable macroeconomic situation, measures are periodically reviewed and the requirements for ensuring the solvency of insurance organizations are raised. The regulator of the Uzbek insurance market (Agency for the Development of the Insurance Market under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan) - in order to tighten state financial control of the solvency and financial stability of insurers, proposes to introduce new standards for the minimum size of the authorized capital, adopts regulatory documents governing the operating and investment activities of

insurers, initiates the translation of the reporting of insurance companies into an international format.

The insurance market, being a part of the market in general, has essential or attributive features. The main attribute of the insurance market is its product (product) - insurance coverage. The policyholder buys insurance coverage in the insurance market in order to achieve his main goal - to protect his property interests from possible losses that may occur as a result of dangerous accidental events. The insurer creates an insurance product, realizing the same goal - to protect the property interests of the insured. For all participants in protective relations, it is important to preserve the wealth of society - material, cultural values, natural resources, ecological balance, human health. But the insurer, as an entrepreneur, has another goal - making a profit. This reveals the dual nature of the insurer: accepting the risk of losses from dangerous accidental events, the insurer itself is the bearer of the insurance risk, that is, the financial risk of loss of profit due to the realization of the risk of losses of the insured from dangerous accidental events.

The financial stability of an insurance company, regulated by the state, can be defined as the ability of the organization to fulfill its obligations to other market participants in the past and present.

At present, in insurance science, the methodology for leveling the contradictions of participants in insurance relations through the use of the methodology of conflict-compromise management is widely discussed in order to achieve local compromises between the insured and the insurer. Achieving a local compromise boils down to the fact that between the insurer and the policyholder there are new types of relations that are implemented in tariff, financial, marketing strategies. In general, this entails a revision of the "redistribution model" of the insurance market. It becomes possible to move from the "compensation" relationship of the insurer and the policyholder to the "protective" insurance relationship. The protective insurance relationship between the policyholder and the insurer is manifested in the transformation of the protective function of insurance into a risk one, and then into a preventive one. Without such transformation, it is impossible to achieve the main goal of insurance - to protect the property interests of policyholders.

Reducing insurance payments through risk prevention and limiting the amount of losses from dangerous accidental events entails strengthening the solvency of the insurance company.

The solvency of an insurance company is an external manifestation of the financial stability of an insurance company, that is, its ability to cover financial liabilities at the expense of liquid assets. The main financial resource of an insurance company is insurance premiums paid by the insured under insurance contracts, which the insurer accumulates in insurance reserves created by insurers to prevent, limit and eliminate losses from dangerous accidental events. But insurance reserves are also the main investment resource of the insurer. Thus, the less insurance reserves are spent, the higher the investment potential, the more the insurer can earn investment income, buy the highest quality assets.

Reducing the value of insurance payments by preventing risks is the most effective method of strengthening the solvency of an insurance company.

If the insurance market returns to the practice of preventing insurance risks in order to reduce the likelihood of insured events, it will become possible to achieve a local compromise in the conflicting goals of the participants in insurance relations. Reducing the amount of insurance payments, which are the main expense item of an insurance company, will increase the insurance company's solvency.

Prevention of risks and, as a result, reduction of losses that the insurer pays from insurance reserves will allow the insurer to reduce insurance rates. The reduction in insurance rates entails an increase in the availability of insurance services, both for citizens and for enterprises. This is a fundamental factor in increasing the effective demand for insurance services.

So, the management of the financial stability of insurance organizations is inextricably linked with the risk management of the insurer. Contradictions for the purposes of the insurer and the policyholder can be resolved by reaching local compromises between the participants in the insurance relationship. Risk prevention will reduce the likelihood of insured events and the amount of losses from the implementation of insurance risks, and, as a result, reduce the costs of the insurer for payments. Thus, the main goals of the participants in insurance economic relations can be harmonized.

In turn, a decrease in the size of insurance payments entails strengthening the financial stability of the insurance organization. The reduction in payments will also allow the insurer to reduce the size of insurance rates, which will help to increase the effective demand for insurance services and improve the efficiency of the insurance market as a whole.

